

H²IOSC
Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

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AUTHORS	Marta Caradonna, Nicola Giampietro, Lisa Reggiani
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ABSTRACT

The present report (Deliverable 7.1 of the H2IOSC project) presents the results of the first phase of activity in WP7, centered on a landscaping survey of prospective users input. The results of the survey are put in context and a SWOT analysis thereof is provided, in order to identify an essential to-do list. The relation to other activities in the WP is briefly sketched in conclusion.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
CLARIN-IT	CLARIN Italian node (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)
DARIAH-IT	DARIAH Italian node (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS Italian node (European Heritage Science Research Infrastructure)
OPERAS	OPERAS Italian node (Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities)
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union

INTRODUCTION

WP7 is intended to provide a first base for the operational use of the H2IOSC cloud platform by researchers. Its objective is to define and implement a series of innovation-oriented services and proof-of-concept sets of resources for direct use by researchers in the form of Pilot applications hosted on the H2IOSC platform.

In this development, input from the project landscaping activities and specific surveys of user needs will allow proper involvement of the research community in co-designing the resulting environment. This input is provided in the WP by task 7.1, in strict collaboration with WP2. The latter is, in this early phase, the principal inter-WP connection for WP7, that will eventually receive essential input from WP5 and WP4, and collect contributions from WP6. Such interconnections or overlapping between WPS also requires a systemic approach oriented at analyzing present and future challenges at a more general level.

WP7 activities have as a pre-condition that user groups from the national research community, as well as contributions from the European counterpart of the national RIs, will be involved/included in the design process from the early phases. Task 7.1 warrants this pre-condition, and more specifically aims at identifying the challenges that characterize the present state of the research communities that the H2IOSC pilots are offered to and the perception that stakeholders have of those challenges.

WP7 starting challenges in relation to task 7.1:

- The identification and interception of technological innovations in according with WP2;
- Monitoring the evolution of needs of the users and providers of the marketplace in accordance with WP2.

Specific tasks for WP - 7.1:

- Leveraging services, surveys, focus groups, and experts debate;
- Identifying shared and unique challenges for the H2IOSC research communities;
- Assessing the perception that stakeholders have of those challenges;
- Analyzing and modeling the results with standard qualitative analysis techniques;
- Provide recommendations (that in this report will take the form of a to-do list).

STARTING SCENARIO

“The Commission has adopted a strategy on Web 4.0 and virtual worlds in order to support the next technological transition and ensure that EU citizens, businesses and EU citizens, businesses and public administrations an open, trusted, secure, fair and inclusive digital trustworthy, fair and inclusive digital environment”¹.

¹ © Union européenne, 2023. ISBN 978-92-68-05543-4. doi:10.2759/541218.KK-07-23-250-FR-N.

Based on this proposal, the EU estimates that global virtual world investment will grow from €27bn in 2022 to €800bn in 2030. In addition, in the virtual worlds sub-sector, by 2022, 3,700 companies, research institutes and government agencies in the EU will increase to 860,000 in 2023.

Sharing this broad horizon, the H2IOSC community's shared challenge forecasting work was undertaken.

Due to the fragmented nature and complexity of the SSH Italian scenario, the survey identifying shared and unique challenges for the H2IOSC research communities is underway through different research tools – questionnaire, focus group and experts debate - to meet as many innovative needs and expectations as possible of users and providers within the research community.

To date, a web questionnaire was developed, tested and distributed and a focus group was planned.

The circulation of the questionnaire –which had been available online for three weeks (September-October 2023)– until now was limited to the main institutional channels. In order to avoid a sectoral approach, it will be extended beyond the channels already utilized to meet the needs of larger and more relevant target audiences, in particular younger segments.

The methodology used to carry out the survey and a few initial results, that allow to identify some key challenges for the H2IOSC Project, are presented in the following section.

THE SURVEY: METHODOLOGY AND PRINCIPAL RESULTS

METHODOLOGY

The survey has been conducted in WP2 and is aimed at outlining a detailed panorama in the language technologies, humanities, and heritage science in Italy, taking into account existing projects, resources, tools, communities, best practices, and standards in use that need to be onboarded in the national marketplace and in the national nodes of the four RIs.

According to WP7 (activity 7.1) it aims at defining and implementing some innovation-oriented services for SSH researchers.

Each RI collaborated on structuring the questionnaire in a way that different sections and questions would be tailored for the different target communities.

Relevant goals for **CLARIN** were to identify all repositories and existing language resources (corpora in different modalities, lexical and conceptual resources, language models, and tools for language processing) in Italy not yet hosted in the national CLARIN repository. Specifically, the questionnaire had to allow to assess the degree of readiness, interoperability, and FAIRness, the potential for visibility, as well as eventual curation needs, of these resources with the aim to prioritize and include them into the ILC4CLARIN repository, the CLARIN four

points of access (VLO, Switchboard, Federated Content Search, Resource Families), and the H2IOSC marketplace (in WP5).

Similarly, for **DARIAH**, relevant goals concerned harvesting data and images about scholarly editions, textual corpora, archives, libraries, artwork resources and catalogs, digital samples and datasets, and materials related to Technical Art History. Along with the harvesting and survey process the current FAIRness status and the employed standards are to be investigated. DARIAH is to inquire about community needs for the domains of reference to create a catalog of resources that will act as a consultation base.

In the case of **E-RIHS**, the goal was: i) to survey all resources (datasets, digital services, and tools) of the scientific communities of Heritage Science and related fields; ii) to understand the level of advance concerning heritage knowledge and innovative strategies for its conservation. In summary, the need for E-RIHS was to gather information concerning standards, protocols, domain ontologies, good practices, guidelines, and shared methodologies for the acquisition, analysis, processing of scientific datasets, and the representation of their results; assessment of the digital resources produced by the E-RIHS.it partners; the description of E-RIHS scientific communities' needs to improve the accessibility, interoperability and reuse of scientific data.

Finally, for **OPERAS**, the goals concerned collecting i) the level of awareness about Open Science and FAIR principles; ii) information about the Open publishing system in Italy, with a non-exclusive focus on journals and books and attention to peculiar kinds and styles of publication in H+CH disciplines; iii) the researchers' publishing needs, taking into account specific Humanities communication channels (to be mapped and contribute to the OPERAS Pathfinder service in WP3); iv) information for developing a toolset for the evaluation of publications and datasets FAIRness; and v) identifying tools, services, and training to meet the scientific community needs related to opening and FAIRifying specific publications channels and types.

Questionnaire specific objectives

- Gathering information from (sub-)communities of our IRs useful for achieving WP objectives;
- Identifying:
 - **Priorities:** data and tools to be soon integrated into H2IOSC (WP3,5,6,7);
 - **Resources needing improvement:** already available in IRs, but in need of improvement with respect to FAIR principles;
 - **Gaps:** Resources not yet available in IR, but very useful/used in the Italian community;
 - **Training needs (for WP8):** knowledge and skill gaps within the target audience is crucial for designing effective training programs, materials, and campaigns.

Target respondent groups

Having defined the objectives and goals of each RI, the next step was to define the ideal target respondents that could provide relevant and valuable insights. Given the broad spectrum of this first survey, ideal respondent groups vary from, and are not limited to, students, researchers, professors, and subject matter experts, working within the the social science, digital humanities, and cultural heritage research domains.

Survey dissemination strategy and deployment

The questionnaire was designed to be distributed online among the *disciplinary communities* relevant to the four infrastructures involved with the purpose of mapping their technological pulse. The service chosen for its realization and deployment is Lime Survey, (<https://www.limesurvey.org/>), for which CNR offers licenses and server hosting as a central service. Furthermore, for meaningful statistical analysis of the data, the survey is deployed in steps. First, it was sent to a selected and restricted group of colleagues, representative of different subcommunities, that acted as a test group and provided useful feedback that led to substantial improvements to the questionnaire. Then the survey was launched to a closed group (i.e. a group of respondents for which we could know the exact numerosity) that would constitute a kind of control group for sampling and statistical purposes. Finally, it will be opened to the wider community.

Before presenting the main findings, it's important to note that this strategy influenced the data evidence. As we shall see, some targets are not present in the survey. This is due to the fact that the distribution lists were very specific. They included the closest and most consistent stakeholders to the RIs. At this stage, young students (18-25 years of Bachelor/Master) are absent or under-represented (Fig.1), while researchers and academics aged 36-50 and 51 and over are over-represented (Fig.2).

As the project develops, both the channels and the target will be increased so that all *target respondents* will be included.

PRINCIPAL RESULTS

In three weeks, 79 respondents completed the entire questionnaire. The results are almost in percentage values.

Fig. 1 Percentage distribution of respondents by age group. (a.v. 79)

Fig. 2 Percentage distribution of respondents by career position. (a.v. 79)

Data collected on age and career confirmed the distribution strategy and its limits: to date, the survey is circumscribed to the H2IOSC community and doesn't include students.

Fig. 3 Percentage distribution of respondents who have created a new digital data resource. (a.v. 79)

Fig. 4 Percentage distribution of respondents who had use of digital data resources. (a.v. 79)

Fig. 5 Percentage distribution of respondents claiming to have created/developed new tools digital/technology/software. (a.v. 79)

Fig. 6 Percentage distribution of respondents claiming to have used digital tools/technologies or software. (a.v. 79)

The results show that the majority of respondents created and used data for/from digital sources (fig. 3 and fig. 4). The great majority of respondents (almost 90%) indicated that they never created/developed digital tools (fig. 5). Almost half of respondents (53%) indicated that they have used digital tools/technologies or software.

When asked "which RIs [involved in H2IOSC] do you know?" almost one in two respondents indicated that they know more than one of the four RIs (fig. 7).

As Fig. 8 shows, almost half of respondents (47%) indicated that they regularly or occasionally use the IRs services; the other half (49%) said that they do not use the services but they are interested.

Fig. 7 RI involved in H2IOSC by respondents' knowledge (Multiple responses. A.v. 149)

Fig. 8 RI involved in H2IOSC whose data/technology/software or services respondents say they use (a.v. 79)

H2IOSC CHALLENGES: A PRELIMINARY OVERVIEW ON THE CURRENT SCENARIO AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

A SWOT analysis based on the evidence provided in the 79 answers of questionnaire and a to-do list for the next project steps are presented below.

SWOT Analysis

The following **SWOT analysis** provides a first comprehensive assessment of the situation, to identify the major challenges and to drive the definition and implementation of innovative services for the SSH research community.

It offers a dynamic view of the scenario, exploiting the connections among the four dimensions.

Strengths highlight key positive attributes inherent in the Project, *Weaknesses* negative ones. The two dimensions capture the status quo.

On the other hand, *Opportunities* and *Threats* outline possible future developments, positive and negative respectively.

Therefore, some topics recur throughout the dimensions with different features and facets.

Fig. 9

STRENGTHS

- Most respondents have good digital competences and are willing to enhance them;
- The participating RIs are already known by the majority of respondents;
- Ample training opportunities are identifiable to improve stakeholders' digital skills;
- The current tool for mapping stakeholders' needs is sufficiently sensitive. Most likely the questionnaire can be easily adapted and used as a continuous monitoring tool.

WEAKNESSES

- Fragmentation and heterogeneity in the SSH landscape requires a significant effort of harmonization, standardization and homogenization in this field;
- To date, because of the limited questionnaire distribution data collected and analyzed are too sectoral.

OPPORTUNITIES

- The EU's strong commitment to the digital transition has created an environment favorable for the increase and diffusion of digital competences in the SSH research field;
- Respondents' aptitude to improve and increase their digital competences is high;
- The developed questionnaire can be efficiently used and improved, if necessary, in the more advanced project phases.

THREATS

- The speed of digital innovation;
- Uncertainty about the time needed by users/providers to adapt to digital innovation.

TO-DO List

The following **to-do list** presents future measures to be undertaken in the project development in order to:

- Reinforce and elevate the strengths;
- Minimize the weaknesses or transform them into opportunities;
- Realize the opportunities;
- Avert the threats.

1. According to WP2, to extend the questionnaire distribution to other targets;
2. According to WP3 and WP4, to enhance standardization, alignment and interoperability strategies and activities;
3. To define and implement innovation-oriented services and pilot applications for direct use by researchers and to involve them in co-designing the project environment (WP7);
4. According to WP8, to empower the SSH stakeholders with training programs tailored to their skills at regular high frequency.

RELATION TO OTHER WP ACTIVITIES

Alongside the landscaping activity in task 7.1, a process of overall analysis of the intrinsic interconnection between the services, and design of possible objects and workflows tying a majority of pilot services together, has been initiated (Fig. 11), in order to be able to:

- intersect the landscape of infrastructure service proposals with the landscape resulting from the identified challenges and users' needs;
- provide a testbed for the proactive interconnection between WPs 4, 5, 6, and 7, that represents the developmental backbone of the H2IOSC cloud platform.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
1	PILOT	CONNESSIONE ALL'OGGETTO 'MS'	ATTIVITA'	RI	RICEVE DA	FORNISCE A	CONDIVIDE CON	RANK
2	Speech and Oral archives	?	7.2	CLARIN			n	
3	LLOD platform	receive lexical analyses of mss./mss. collections?	7.2	CLARIN	7.3 lex. an.		7.2	4
4	CLARIN Community Pilot	showcase works? (in a final stage?)	7.2	CLARIN				5
5	Digital Philology HUB	describing, editing, displaying mss.: provide AI-based tools; mss. image management (duplicated elsewhere?)	7.3	DARIAH			7.5	1
6	Digital Heritage and Memory HUB	provide tools?	7.3	DARIAH				3
7	Open Digital Archaeology Hub	innovative technologies for the extraction of structured information from traditional textual and iconographic corpora? (could this be leveraged?)	7.4	E-RIHS				3
8	Open Digital Epigraphy Hub	searchable epigraphic material for intertextuality?	7.4	E-RIHS				3
9	Illuminated manuscript VRE	The action aims at implementing a VRE for illuminated manuscripts investigated by analytical methods.	7.5	E-RIHS			7.2	0
10	Online Platform for Spatial Heritage Science Data management	Geo-referenced material analyses of mss.?	7.5	E-RIHS	7.3	7.3		3
11	HeriVerse-Heritage Science Metaverse	could be a service	7.5	E-RIHS		7.3, 7.11, ogni interazione (p.es. 7.3&7.8)		3
12	Scientific Digital Hub For Painting Collections	Illumination as painting	7.6	E-RIHS	7.3		7.3, 7.11	3
13	Innovative Interfaces	?	7.7	E-RIHS				n
14	Scientific digital hub for metal artworks	bookbinding metal artworks and implements (chains e.g.)?	7.8	E-RIHS	7.3		7.3, 7.11	3
15	Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions	?	7.9	E-RIHS				n
16	Open Resources Publishing Pilot	mss. metadata collections e.g. might be managed here	7.10	OPER...			7.2	4
17	Diamond OA Publishing Hub for Scholarly Editions etc.	"manage and publish scholarly digital editions" (of mss.)	7.11	OPER...	7.3 contenuti e strumenti	7.3 workflow, pubblicazione	7.2	2

Fig. 11